

Kinetic study of iridium(III) catalyzed oxidation of D-mannitol and erythritol by *N*-bromosuccinimide in acidic medium

Sheila Srivastava* and Vandana Gupta

Chemical Laboratories, Feroze Gandhi College, Raebareli-229 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : she_ila72@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 8 June 2006, revised 29 August 2006, accepted 30 August 2006

Abstract : Kinetic investigations on iridium trichloride catalyzed oxidation of D-mannitol and erythritol by acidic solution of *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in the presence of mercuric acetate as a scavenger for Br⁻ have been carried out in the temperature range 30–45 °C. The reactions follow identical kinetics. The rate shows a first-order dependence on [NBS] in lower concentration range which tends to zero-order at its higher concentrations. A first-order dependence on [Ir^{III}] is also observed. Negligible effect of [substrate], [Hg(OAc)₂] and ionic strength have been observed. Addition of [H⁺], [Cl⁻] and succinimide shows a negative effect. Activation parameters have been computed and a suitable mechanism conforming to above results has been proposed.

Keywords : Iridium(III), *N*-bromosuccinimide, D-mannitol.

N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) is a potent oxidant and has been used in the quantitative determination¹. The utility of iridium(III) chloride² as homogeneous catalyst has been reported by several workers but little attention has been paid so far to activity of iridium(III) chloride as catalyst in NBS oxidation. This fact prompted us to undertake the present investigation which constitutes the kinetic study of Ir^{III} catalyzed oxidation of D-mannitol and erythritol by acidic NBS in the presence of Hg(OAc)₂ as a scavenger for Br⁻.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in this experiment were of AnalaR quality. The reactions were initiated (in a thermostat ±0.1 °C) by addition of NBS solution and other reagents equilibrated separately at 35 °C. The progress of the reaction was monitored by determining unconsumed NBS iodometrically at regular intervals, using starch as indicator.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Stoichiometry of the reaction was ascertained by equilibrating the reaction mixture containing an excess of NBS over D-mannitol and erythritol (in varying ratios) at 50 °C for 48 h and determination of residual NBS in different sets showed that one mol of glycol consumed two mol of NBS. The oxidation product D-mannonic acid and erythronic acid were detected by conventional methods.

Results and discussion

The kinetic results are given in Table 1. First-order dependence in NBS was followed at lower NBS concentration which tended to zero-order at higher concentrations which is clear from the plot of *k* versus NBS (Fig. 1). The reaction was observed to be independent of [substrate] i.e. zero-order with respect to both D-mannitol

Fig. 1. Plot of *k* and [NBS] in oxidation of D-mannitol (A) and erythritol (B) · [Ir^{III}] = 6.70 × 10⁻⁶ M, [HClO₄] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, [KCl] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, [substrate] = 2.00 × 10⁻² M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 1.25 × 10⁻³ M, temp 35 °C

Table 1. Effect of reactants on the reaction rate

$[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 6.67 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, temp. 35 °C

$10^4 [\text{NBS}]$ (M)	$10^2 [\text{S}]$ (M)	$10^7 (k) \text{ ML}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$		$10^4 (k_1) \text{ s}^{-1}$	
		D-Mannitol	Erythritol	D-Mannitol	Erythritol
6.67	2.00	1.52	1.98	2.28	3.26
8.00	2.00	1.77	2.64	2.21	3.30
10.00	2.00	2.22	3.18	2.22	3.18
12.50	2.00	2.56	3.92	2.04	3.10
16.67	2.00	2.60	4.00	1.56	2.34
20.00	2.00	2.62	3.98	1.31	2.00
25.00	2.00	2.58	4.04	1.03	1.62
10.00	0.33	2.30	3.20	-	-
10.00	0.40	2.10	3.24	-	-
10.00	0.50	2.34	3.30	-	-
10.00	0.67	2.20	3.12	-	-
10.00	1.00	2.36	3.14	-	-
10.00	4.00	2.24	3.08	-	-

and erythritol. First-order dependence on $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ is observed and a slope value of 3.33 s^{-1} for D-mannitol and 4.52 s^{-1} for erythritol is obtained from the k vs $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ plot (Fig. 2). Negative effect in $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is seen.

Successive addition of succinimide decreases the oxidation rate whereas the influence of the addition of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ and variation in ionic strength is negligible (Table 2). The kinetics were studied at different temperatures (30–45 °C). The values of entropy of activation

(ΔS^*), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) are shown in Table 2.

In acidic solution, iridium trichloride exists as $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$. It has also been reported that $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$ is involved in the following equilibrium :

Thus either $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$ or $[\text{IrCl}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2-}$ may act as catalytic species. If $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$ is taken as catalytic species, the rate law would require positive effect of chloride ions contrary to the negative effect of chloride ions on the oxidation rate observed by us. Hence the only choice is $[\text{IrCl}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2-}$ which when assumed as a real species of iridium trichloride in acidic medium explains the negative effect of chloride ions.

Thus NBS itself, or any of Br^+ , HOBr and N^+BSH may be the possible oxidizing species. If NBS as such is taken as the reactive species, then the rate law should be independent of succinimide contrary to its negative effect. This rules out the possibility of involvement of NBS as such in the reaction. If either protonated NBS, i.e. (N^+BSH) or Br^+ is assumed to be involved in the reaction, either positive effect of H or first-order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$, is required contrary to the negative effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the oxidation rate, observed by us. Hence participation of these species in the reaction is ruled out. In light of the above statements, the only choice left is HOBr . The rate law derived on the basis of HOBr as active species of NBS, explains all kinetic orders and kinetic effects observed in the present redox system. Hence HOBr is taken as effective reactive species of NBS.

Fig. 2. Plot of k and $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ in oxidation of D-mannitol (B) and erythritol (A) : $[\text{NBS}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{substrate}] = 2.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, temp. 35 °C.

The oxygen atom present in the complex formed in step (5) becomes electron deficient due to a coordinate bond formation between the oxygen atom lone pair in (OBr^-) and Ir^{III} or $[\text{IrCl}_5]^{2-}$. This will polarize the O-Br bond in the direction of oxygen making Br slightly positive. Consequently, the electrophilic character and hence the hydride ion abstracting capacity of HOBr is enhanced considerably after complexation, leading to its interaction with glycol molecule. The formation of $[\text{IrCl}_5(\text{H})]^{3-}$ is well established⁴.

Application of steady state treatment with reasonable approximation yields rate law

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{K'[\text{NBS}] [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{K'' [\text{NBS}] + [\text{H}^+] [\text{NHS}] \{K_2 + [\text{Cl}^-]\}} \quad (11)$$

where $K' = K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4$, $K'' = K_1 K_2 K_3$

An increase in $[\text{Cl}^-]$ will direct equilibrium (3) to the

left side, causing decrease in concentration of the catalytic species $[\text{IrCl}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2-}$ which result in the decrease of oxidation rate. This supports the assumption that $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$ dissociates to liberate Cl^- and thus $[\text{IrCl}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2-}$ is in fact the active catalytic species of iridium(III) chloride.

Conclusion :

It is concluded from the present investigation that HOBr and $[\text{IrCl}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2-}$ are the reactive species of NBS and iridium(III) chloride in acidic medium respectively.

References

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